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Scaling up distributed solar PV adoption in Ghana's commercial sector

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Summary

Solar PV presents a promising solution to the high energy costs and unreliable grid supply facing Ghana's commercial sector. Yet despite strong solar potential and clear economic and environmental benefits, adoption remains limited. Based on interviews with 23 hotels and real estate companies across 4 cities, this study identifies key drivers and persistent barriers shaping solar PV uptake in Ghana's hotel and real estate sectors.

Businesses that have adopted solar are motivated primarily by long-term cost savings, improved energy reliability, and reputational benefits – not by government incentives. For many, this is a pragmatic investment to cut energy bills, reduce diesel dependence, and enhance their brand as environmentally responsible companies. In real estate, solar can also increase property value and market appeal.

However, high upfront costs, limited access to finance, and doubts about solar performance continue

Figure 1: Rooftop solar installation in real estate development in Obosomase

to hinder uptake. Weak implementation of existing policies, such as the Net Metering Scheme, means that policy support is limited, while the prospect of maintenance challenges often acts a further deterrent. Additionally, some decision-makers hold negative perceptions about solar PV, exacerbated by weak public

awareness and a lack of accessible, sector-specific guidance.

To close the gap between interest and action, Ghana must improve policy delivery, increase visibility of success stories, and support informed decision-making, ensuring solar becomes a viable, trusted option for more businesses.

Policy recommendations

- **Implement the Net Metering Scheme**, ensuring fair treatment of prosumers, and accelerate deployment of advanced metering infrastructure.
- **Provide targeted financial incentives** – such as grants and tax relief – and **build financial sector capacity** to expand loan access and embed solar programmes into commercial and housing finance systems.
- **Promote reputational incentives** such as green certifications, awards, and public recognition to reward businesses adopting clean energy solutions.
- **Support targeted training and outreach** to empower internal solar champions, engage CEOs and boards, and raise sector-specific awareness through business associations and real-world solar success stories.
- **Strengthen solar market quality assurance** by certifying installers, enforcing technical standards, and expanding after-sales service to build trust and ensure long-term system reliability.

Figure 2: Rooftop solar PV installation on a Sunyani hotel

Introduction

Ghana's commercial sector faces systemic energy challenges, including frequent power outages and high electricity costs [1–3]. These issues stem from strong reliance on grid supply, which leaves consumers vulnerable to infrastructure failures and persistently high tariffs. In response, many firms resort to diesel-powered generators as a backup, further exposing them to volatile fossil fuel markets and exacerbating local environmental pollution [1–3].

In this context, solar photovoltaic (PV) is a cost-effective alternative for Ghana's commercial

sector [2–4]. With abundant solar resources available year-round across the country, solar PV offers a reliable means of decentralised energy generation. By reducing dependence on the national grid and diesel generators, businesses can benefit from more stable and predictable energy pricing, enhancing their ability to manage long-term operating costs [5, 6]. Moreover, on-site solar deployment supports Ghana's national emissions reduction targets while delivering co-benefits such as job creation, environmental sustainability, and enhanced corporate reputation [2, 3, 5].

Despite this potential, the adoption of solar technologies in Ghana's commercial sector remains limited [8, 9]. This slow uptake is driven by persistent techno-economic and policy-related barriers, including restricted access to consumer credit and inadequate government support [9, 10]. These constraints have significantly hindered market development, including in urban areas where commercial demand for reliable and affordable power is highest.

This Policy Report investigates the root causes of this limited adoption and provides a comprehensive overview of the key barriers and enabling factors shaping Ghana's commercial solar landscape. It further proposes a set of concrete policy recommendations designed to accelerate market growth and enhance the viability of solar solutions.

Methods

To provide a clear picture of the dynamics of solar PV adoption in Ghana's commercial sector, and particularly within the hotel and real estate industries, the study employed a qualitative case study research design, supported by site visits and semi-structured interviews with company representatives (eg energy managers, facility engineers, directors). Data was collected between September and October 2024 across four cities in Ghana: Accra, Kumasi, Sunyani, and Koforidua.

A total of 25 people were interviewed from the hospitality and real estate sectors (see **Table 1**). In the real estate sector, 6 out of 11 businesses

interviewed used solar, while 5 did not. In the hotel sector, only 3 hotels had adopted solar, whereas 9 had not. The commercial activities also reflected different sub-categories within both the hotel and real estate sectors, providing a diverse perspective on solar PV adoption.

In addition, two representatives were interviewed from business associations: the Ghana Real Estate Developers Association (GREDA) and Ghana Hotels Association. These participants provided baseline information on the challenges and prospects confronting solar PV uptake in the commercial sector.

Table 1: Key Features of Interviews

Feature	Hotels	Real estate companies
No. of respondents/cases	12	11
Sector category	2 to 5 stars	A1+ to A4
Employees	8 to 400	6 to 200
Use of solar	3 out of 12	6 out of 11
Primary energy source	Grid (9); Grid and solar (3)	Grid (8); Solar (2); Grid and solar (1)
Secondary energy source	Genset (12)	Genset (8); Grid (1); Genset and solar (1); Solar (1)
Monthly Energy Consumption (kWh)	11,852 to 780,000	Data not available
Awareness of government policies	3 out of 12	5 out of 11

Results

Ghana's policy framework for distributed solar

Ambitious renewable policy frameworks and direct financial incentives such as grants, subsidies, and tax breaks can play a crucial role in motivating businesses to invest in solar PV. Table 2 provides an overview of Ghana's renewable energy policies and regulations. The country has established several strategic frameworks, such as the *Renewable Energy Act 2011* and the *Renewable Energy Master Plan* of 2019, but their implementation has been partial and uneven. Ghana's slow progress in solar PV diffusion is widely attributed to a lack of political will, inadequate coordination between government agencies, and weak institutional frameworks [11–14].

In the case of distributed solar PV, Ghana introduced a Net Metering Scheme in 2015 intended to enable small-scale renewable energy producers to export surplus electricity to the grid in exchange for credits [10]. However, the scheme

has faced significant implementation challenges. Resistance from electricity distribution companies – driven by structural debt and a business model that conflicts with the inclusion of prosumers – has hindered uptake and effectiveness [6, 15, 16]. Lack of transparent tariff pricing and universal access to the net-meters are also identified as additional barriers [6, 15, 16].

Most interviewees demonstrated a limited awareness of government policies and available incentives for solar adoption. This suggests that government support is either poorly communicated or insufficiently targeted. In many cases, the perceived absence of government support reinforces the notion that adopting solar is a private or commercial initiative rather than a policy-driven one. As a result, decisions to invest in solar PV are often driven by other factors, such as dissatisfaction with grid reliability or long-term cost savings, rather than a direct response to public policy. Drivers of adoption are discussed in the next section.

Table 2: Summary of Key Renewable Energy (RE) Policies and Regulations in Ghana [17–19]

No.	Key RE Policy	Focus	Target/Impact	Policy Issue	Status
1.	Renewable Energy Act, 2011	Legal framework for RE	Feed-in tariffs, licensing, RE Fund	Inadequate power sector regulations Lack of transparent tariff pricing Lack of full policy implementation	Active
2.	Energy Sector Strategy and Development Plan, 2010	Energy diversification	Support the National Economic Development Agenda	The plan was generic, incomplete, and not systematically designed	Not Active
3.	Renewable Energy Master Plan, 2019	Action plan for RE technology	1,363 MW RE capacity, decentralised RE electrification options in 1,000 off-grid communities	Lack of coordination among institutions and the RE expert	Active
4.	Energy Transition Framework, 2022	Climate-aligned transition	Net-zero by 2070, promote electric vehicles and RE	Weak institutional capacity Inadequate funding for green technology innovation Lack of political commitment and full policy implementation	Active
5.	Net Metering Scheme, 2015	Distributed solar generation	Incentives for Solar PV installers	Financial constraints and technical challenges Rigid nature of the electricity tariff structure Reluctance of electricity distribution companies to accept prosumers	Active
6.	Strategic National Energy Plan (2006–2020)	Provision of sufficient, viable, and efficient energy services	To increase the use of RE by 10% in 2020	Lack of pricing regulations for RE products	Not Active

Drivers and barriers to solar adoption

The study showed that hotels and real estate businesses depend largely on the grid as their primary source of electricity and on diesel generators as the main source of electricity backup. Where solar has been adopted, its use varies across different commercial activities. In the hotel sector, for example, solar installations consisted entirely of hybrid systems with the grid, with diesel as a backup. Whereas in the real estate sector solar was used as the primary source of energy, in hybrid systems, or as a backup.

Drivers of adoption

Although participants often expressed strong interest in solar technologies, actual adoption rates remained low. The primary motivations cited for considering or installing solar PV include the prospect of long-term cost savings, a commitment to environmental sustainability, and the desire to enhance energy reliability.

The potential for significant long-term **energy cost savings** serves as the most powerful incentive for businesses to adopt. For example, the hotel sector tends to have high electricity-related expenses (up to US\$ 66,000 per month in very large high-end hotels) between grid tariffs and fuel for diesel generators. For some of these businesses, solar PV can prove a fruitful investment, as one interviewee explained:

“... it took the hotel three years, nine months to guarantee a return on investment.” (Hotel Manager)

Although real estate developers may not directly reap the long-term energy savings, integrating solar installations can significantly enhance the appeal of their properties to buyers who prioritise lower utility costs and sustainable living, thus strengthening their business case. This was reported by a real estate developer:

“When people come and find out that we're using solar water heaters... they get encouraged. That's how come we sold out very quickly. It's one of the reasons we sold out.” (Real Estate Developer)

Some participants also discussed the potential of solar PV to provide a **consistent energy supply**. Despite a high degree of electrification across the country, Ghana's businesses face challenges with unreliable electricity supply and power outages, leading to reliance on backup diesel generators which in turn contribute to high costs, local pollution, and emissions. Those participants who had adopted solar pointed to the benefits of having diversified their energy supply, reducing dependence on the national grid, for example:

“Now we don't run out of hot water anymore. Even if the power goes off, the solar takes over... The guests like it.” (Hotel Facilities Manager)

The **environmental benefits** of solar were also discussed by a few participants who noted that solar PV installations align with efforts to promote sustainable energy practices and protect the environment. For most solar adopters, this was a major drive behind their decision across the hospitality and real estate sector. A real estate development utilities manager noted:

“The other [reason] has to do with environmental stewardship. I think as a world-class developer, [...] investments in solar sell us as green investors, and then we are seen as responsible global citizens.” (Real Estate Development Utilities Manager)

A commitment to sustainability is often closely aligned with efforts to elevate **company image**. Participants argued that solar PV, with its strong green brand associations, has become a key reputational asset. A hotel manager explained how adopting solar can credibly signal

environmental leadership to other stakeholders:

“*Solar energy not only enhanced our company's image but also positioned it as a forward-thinking and environmentally conscious business.*” (Hotel Manager)

Importantly, energy decisions in the commercial sector were typically shaped by centralised **leadership structures**, with boards, CEOs, or owners holding decisive authority. Where leadership was engaged and environmentally conscious, solar uptake was far more likely. In some hotels, however, solar discussions were also being driven by proactive non-executive staff, such as facility or energy managers, who had acquired technical knowledge and were building internal support for change. While these “solar champions” can play a pivotal role in influencing leadership, their efforts are often constrained as discussed in the next section.

In the real estate sector, **investors** were found to greatly shape sustainability decisions. For example, developers with foreign ownership or exposure often framed solar adoption as part of a broader environmental commitment, as stated by this Belgian real estate developer operating in Ghana: “Sustainability is for us a foundation point in everything”. Moreover, large international real estate groups can often draw on more experience with solar technologies:

“*We were a little bit lucky because our funding company had already done several developments across Africa... They had used these materials [solar] before in Angola and it had worked very well for them... So they were only bringing down a technology that had worked in another African country.*”

(Real Estate Marketing and Operations Manager)

Barriers to adoption

Overall, all participants pointed to **high upfront costs** as the largest barrier to solar adoption in both the real estate and hotel sector. There was a

widespread perception that solar technologies are prohibitively expensive, deterring many from considering this type of investment, as noted by this participant:

“*The company would consider installing solar PV systems if the cost of solar energy and installation becomes cheaper compared to the grid and diesel generator set.*” (Real Estate Site Engineer)

Secondly, **negative perceptions** on the performance of solar technologies frequently undermined adoption. Some potential users viewed solar PV as unreliable, doubting its ability to power all appliances effectively. This is compounded by the concern that solar electricity cannot be stored and that it cannot satisfy energy needs, amplifying hesitancy toward embracing these solutions, as discussed by a Real Estate Site Engineer:

“*Solar energy is unreliable as it restricts users from using all their electrical appliances, especially air conditioners, fridges.*” (Real Estate Site Engineer)

Even where pro-environmental values were present, **limited technical understanding** often undermined solar investment. Participants from the hotel sector frequently reported partial or limited knowledge or negative perceptions about solar reliability. Several said they struggled to access clear information about solar and felt confused, emphasising the need for a dedicated, consumer-focused body to guide both households and businesses. In the absence of reliable information, informal narratives can dominate, ultimately discouraging investment, as a hotel manager explained:

“*If I had the knowledge and it's more efficient, more reliable... I'd definitely go for solar PV. But with the small research I did, I was still going to rely on grid electricity... I didn't get enough knowledge.*”

(Hotel Manager)

Adoption was also slowed by concerns about the **quality of solar panels** available on the market and difficulties in sourcing replacement components for inverters. Further, **maintenance challenges**, such as roof leakages caused by substandard workmanship, amplified concerns for businesses considering solar installations.

Together, these issues pose significant risks:

“*We used to have some leakages in the roof, so management uninstalled the solar panels, fixed a new roofing material, and never re-installed the panels again.*” (Hotel Front Desk Supervisor).

As discussed in the previous section, company **leadership** can be an important driver for adoption. However, in hotels, existing hierarchies often stalled adoption, despite technical staff support, as energy engineers advocated internally but lacked authority. One Accra hotel's board rejected a fully financed solar proposal over “financial control” concerns; in another, the owner unilaterally removed the solar system. Overall, many participants expressed environmental

concerns or interest in renewables, but these values are not institutionalised in hotel policy or planning, reducing support for solar projects.

Such dynamics reinforce **behavioural barriers** rooted in perceptions of risk, mistrust in system performance, and aversion to large upfront costs. Several interviewees noted the dominance of short-term thinking or cost aversion at the senior level. Many decision-makers view solar as financially risky, focusing on large upfront costs and ignoring long-term savings. As one participant put it:

“*The cost is huge, they would not even venture.*” (Hotel Energy Manager)

The analysis also identified **bureaucracy as a barrier**. Participants mentioned obstacles such as burdensome bureaucracy in general, as potential users and installers of renewable energy technology often struggle with obtaining legal permits during the installation process:

“*People always get frustrated in doing the right thing.*” (Real Estate Business Owner)

Key insights

Despite limited government support, some businesses in Ghana's commercial sector have adopted solar PV, driven primarily by commercial pragmatism rather than public policy. Despite concerns about high upfront costs, the potential for significant long-term cost savings remains attractive, proving solar a viable and cost-effective solution for the country's commercial energy needs. The following insights and recommendations identify opportunities to accelerate solar uptake.

Although Ghana has developed several renewable energy policies, including the **Renewable Energy Act and the Net Metering Scheme**, implementation remains weak.

Resistance from distribution companies, unclear tariff structures, and poor coordination between agencies have hindered progress.

Revising and enforcing these schemes is critical to guarantee fair treatment of prosumers and streamline grid integration. At the same time, **smart financial incentives could lower the barrier of upfront costs and unlock investment** – for example, through targeted tax relief and grants – particularly among small and mid-sized businesses.

Engaging financial institutions in renewable energy initiatives is also essential to enhance their understanding of the solar energy sector, enabling more informed decisions on loans

and funding. This support can accelerate solar adoption and help reform housing finance requirements to promote greater accessibility and inclusivity.

Beyond financial savings, businesses are often motivated by the desire for greater energy reliability, environmental commitment, and a desire to improve the company's image. This suggests that, beyond financial incentives, **there is a clear opportunity to promote solar PV adoption by strengthening reputational incentives** – such as through green certifications, public awards, and official recognition – for businesses that invest in sustainable energy solutions.

Many businesses overlook solar due to persistent preconceived notions about cost and reliability, fueled by a lack of accessible, trustworthy information. Participants called for **a dedicated, consumer-focused body to offer clear, sector-specific guidance**. To shift perceptions and boost adoption, stronger communication, targeted outreach, and the promotion of real success stories are essential. Business associations should lead this effort – engaging solar PV installers, sharing practical examples, and highlighting both benefits and challenges – to build trust and reduce the perceived risks of investing in solar.

Leadership and organisational dynamics also emerged as central. In a highly centralised decision-making environment, the support of owners, CEOs, or boards is essential. Where leadership is environmentally engaged or financially forward-looking, solar adoption is far more likely. In some cases, technical staff acted as internal champions for solar PV, but their efforts were often undermined by risk-averse leadership. **Building internal capacity, through training for energy managers and targeted outreach to decision-makers**, could empower these “solar champions” and help shift organisational priorities.

Finally, **concerns around product quality and maintenance must be addressed**. Strengthening quality assurance and supply chains for solar PV equipment through installer certifications, enforcing technical standards, and expanding after-sales services can reduce mistrust and improve user experience.

If Ghana is to scale up distributed solar meaningfully, its policy approach must become not only ambitious, but actionable, trusted, and tightly aligned with how businesses actually make decisions.

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